

Affected Factors on Public Promotion Projects in Thailand: A Case of Participation Action State Policies

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 05, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Capacity building on Public Health promotion, Public participation projects, Health Impact Assessment evaluation</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5071212</p>	<p><i>Integrated Enhancement of Health Program and Development of Health Mechanism at Area Level</i> Project was an integrated project among The Office of the Thai Health Promotion Foundation (ThaiHealth), National Health Security Office (NHSO), and the Ministry of Public Health, Thailand, to operate health promotion tasks and develop health mechanisms in rural areas. The purpose of the project concentrated on public participation which was the new political policy on promoting and encouraging democratic decentralization according to the 1997 Thailand Constitution. By document analyzing the final reports of 4 Area Health's in Northeastern region, Thailand, we found that there were different levels of the project success affected by process, people, and program factors of the public participation projects. The well-balanced relationship roles between the state and practitioners were the dominant success factor among the networks participation, and the project's context should not exceed the communities responsiveness ones. Moreover, the practitioners at village level asked for adequate knowledge and necessary information concerning the project before and during the projects implementations. Feedbacks from the project's implement groups were also reported that they need professional facilitators from the state sectors as mentors throughout the projects.</p>

Introduction

World Health Organization (WHO) had revised some new terms on Health Promotion Glossary for clear understanding among those who set the health promotion's policies or took the actions. The new terms were based on broadening understanding that "health is shaped by individual factors and the physical, social, economic and political context in which people live" (Smith, Tang and Nutbeam, 2006). Collaboration among organizations, practitioners and communities was also mentioned under a new term of capacity building to enable health promotion effectiveness. A case study of an integrated public health promotion project that took place in Thailand where her communities were new to participate in the action state policies should reflect enabling capacity building for Thai rural health promotion effectiveness.

1. Background

1.1 Public Participation

Public participation was said as a main indicator for adequate and sustainable transferring state policies/projects to communities (Zadeh and Ahmad, 2009). With the participation, the policies/projects were analyzed in overall 360 degree perspectives from stakeholders and affected people that led to the consensus on the policies/projects which was an important indicator of the success. Thus, public participation was a significant way to increase the policies/project's quality (Zadeh and Ahmad, 2009; Aarts and Leeuwis, 2010) that the concept has been widely used in several organizations since the 1950s. Multilateral agencies, the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) for example, incorporated the public participation approach into the organizations' policies (Chifamba, 2013). In Thailand's 8th National Economic and Social Development Plan (1997–2001), decentralization policy was also prioritized (Wongpreedee and Mahakanjana, 2011). Public participation could run to disappointing results, too, if it was used without considering the success factors, proper procedures and techniques, adequate resources, and professional facilitators. There were many sectors to consider in successfully transforming the state policies/projects to public as follows (Zadeh and Ahmad, 2009; Aarts and Leeuwis, 2010; Chifamba, 2013; Pagatpathan and Ward, 2017):

1. Role of state as representative of power or political commitment; should be decentralization, willingness to listen, carry out program(s), provided fair information and adequate resources before and during the process, technical assistance, supported deliberative areas for decision-making, partnership synergy and had a well-balanced relationship with the participants, kept the network connected within the other organizations and with the representatives.

2. Role of participants or representative of group participants; should be inclusiveness, proactive, eager to have new skills and experience, responsively took their roles in participation -willing to participate continuously, willing to spend time and resources, dedication to interact and educate the context with others participants as well as with rural officers.

3. Context of the policies/projects; should be in participants' interests such as the policies/projects that affected their communities or nearby ones; not beyond their power limit responsiveness.

4. Procedures and techniques that suit the context; should be clear, transparency, consistency with good communication throughout the procedures.

5. Evaluation and revision that adjusted to the social change. Knowing what activities worked or not in the process.

6. Feedback to the participants on how their suggestion or decision-making was used in the policies/projects. It, also, should be clear, transparent, and be able to sustainability practice in the area.

In summary, public participation was a social active process interacted between the state and community participants to achieve the consensus on the states policies/projects that directly affected the people. Well-defined of each other's roles, context, techniques, evaluation and feedback should be set carefully to reach successful results from the process. The participation was based on political commitments, concentrated on empowerment from the state, thus socio-political of the target community should be analyzed first before transferring the policies/projects.

1.2 Thailand political society

Decentralization was a new-born governance policy in Thailand, a country that had been under the rule of absolute monarchs for over 700 years of her long history. Former Thai kings took their roles as the leaders and the masters of the country with bureaucrat officers served as the royal servants, and village level officers were at the bottom end of the civil administration next to villagers. Thus, the idea of a controlled center authority had been deeply rooted in Thai traditional political culture (Sivaraks, 2011). Local empowerment started first on the reign of King Rama V (1868-1910) along with Thailand had to modernize her civil administration to a bureaucratization system with strong centralizing characteristics of the central-provincial-local civil service system (Wongnasri, 2015). The first provincial sanitation district of Thailand was founded at Samut Sakhon Province in 1905 with limited empowerment to look after the area's roads, public health, and primary education. The district administration was under the Ministry of Interior.

Thai villagers had a few opportunities to act their political participation in the political system. Those who lived in rural countries occasionally voted in the elections of their village leaders and members of the House of Representatives while urban country villagers had an added chance to vote in elections of the municipal government. Moreover, traditional Thai bureaucracy had strong resistance for decentralization (Sivaraks, 2011). They used to power hierarchy level on bureaucratization systems where top-down decision-makings were made and transferred from central officials to regional, then provincial, district, sub-district, and villages respectively.

In 1997, Thailand new constitution had promoted and encouraged democratic decentralization policy to strengthen civil society and economies at the village level with a major goal to encourage public participation (Sivaraks, 2011; Wongpreedee and Mahakanjana, 2011). According to the 1997 constitution, all Sanitation Districts changed to Subdistrict Administrative Organizations, another new form of Thailand local governances: the oldest one was Municipalities, founded in 1933 and had 3 organization levels depended on the number of population in the area - city level with populations more than 50,000, town level with populations between 10,000–50,000, and sub-district level with populations less than 10,000, Provincial Administrative Organizations, Bangkok Metropolitan Area, and City of Pattaya (Wongpreedee and Mahakanjana, 2011). The organizational governance structure was in mayor-council form which was selected by direct election from their people in the area (Wongnasri, 2015). All local administrative organizations were supported and promoted on their plans, personnel administration, finance, and administration by the Department of Local Administration, the new government agency in the Ministry of Interior, in order to “strengthen the capacity and efficiency of the local administrative organizations on public service provision” (Department of Local Administration, 2015).

1.3 Thailand Social Conditions

Thailand has had a great impact from rapid socio-economic development since the past decades. She used to be an agricultural society where most people lived in rural areas. Nowadays, Capitalism had been an economical mainstream, urban area expanded to the rural one made it more industrialized and urbanized while regardless of destruction rural environment (Pinyuchon and Gray, 1997; Kaewnaidee, Pholdeeyiam and Pukrittayakamee, 2003). Capitalism increased economic growth of the country so that the government could develop many public utilities for her people. On the other hand, rural laborers have

temporarily moved to work in urban areas to increase their families income, leaving aging people and their children behind.

Social innovation has been said by many Thai social scholars as a way to solve social problems. The dominant one was the Sufficiency economic philosophy of King Bhumibol, King Rama IX of Thailand, which the 12th National Economic and Social Development Plan (2016-2021) had applied it in the plan development in order to promote the peaceful and harmonious society on the basis of strengthening the country for both human capital and society. Thai human capital should be developed in both morality and knowledge including: logical thinking, having consciousness of morality, virtue, being aware of changes, being able to make decisions using the principle of modesty in an ethical life, patient and diligent. (Office of the National Economics and Social Development Board, n.d.)

1.4 The Health Promotion Project

The Office of the Thai Health Promotion Foundation (ThaiHealth), National Health Security Office (NHSO), and the Ministry of Public Health had integrated a project to operate health promotion tasks and develop health mechanisms, by the name -Integrated Enhancement of Health Program and Development of Health Mechanism at Area Level Project. The purpose of the project was to cooperate in enhancing the potential of health promotion teams from both government and private sectors to be able to drive the project objectives via online technology tools. The goal was to reduce the redundancy of work and to expand the larger scope of the working area in the budget amount. The budget would be given to the selected public health promotion projects in any pilot district selected from each Area Health.

The action plans were divided into 2 major plans. The first one was to enhance the team's potential, understanding, and skills in managing health promotion funding projects in order to be able to coach the practitioners or to work as the projects' consultant clinic, and the second one was to imply selected projects in a pilot district which would be done by Quality-of-Life Development committees at district and sub-district level. The evaluation during the project process was done by applying 6 steps of Health Impact assessment (HIA): 1) screening, 2) setting the scope and approaches, 3) evaluating, 4) reviewing the draft report, 5) developing proposals for improvement, and 6) monitoring, evaluating and revising (Sutheravut, 2020).

The selected area where was a pilot district was aimed at achieving 7 aspects: Aspect 1) to obtain information about health problem situation and solution for solving problems, Aspect 2) to create the plan for dealing with the problems, Aspect 3) to improve the quality of the projects, Aspect 4) to obtain the ability to synthesize the results and values, Aspect 5) to receive the ability to conduct a real-time monitoring process of the project, Aspect 6) to do a report of project operation, and Aspect 7) to have a database for the utilization in future.

The complexity of 7 aspects and 6 indicators for HIA's evaluations on the process of the state-designed project made it might be somewhat hard for the Quality-of-Life Development committee, a corporate group among government sector, private sector, and district villagers -according to the 2017 Regulations of the Office of the Prime Minister, to participate and transform the project in their responsive areas. Thus, adequate techniques should essentially apply in the projects' process.

1.5 Northeastern Region and its Area Healths

Northeastern region, Thailand is the largest region area as well as the largest agricultural areas of the country, but the ratio of land ownership per household is lower than the national average. Moreover, the soil is a sandy soil condition that does not hold water, causing water shortage. Furthermore, it is infertility one from rock salt beneath that makes the soil saline. Thus, the use of land for agriculture was restricted with only 11.2 % of the irrigated area in the region. Rain and drought including the low price of agricultural crops had a great impact on average income per household in the Northeastern region which was the second lowest in the country. Although the Northeast population was 33.2 % which was the most of the country, the educational opportunities and educational achievement were the lowest. Most of the workers were educated at elementary school level and 50.77 % were in the agricultural sector. Thus, the workers had temporarily transmigrated into big cities to find jobs as unskilled labor made Northeastern aging people in rural areas increasingly neglected, though their communities were more socially integrated than other regions. (National Research Council of Thailand, 2010; Northeastern Region Development Plan 2017 – 2012: Review Edition, 2010).

According to the largest number of populations, there are 4 Area Health's in the Northeastern region - Area Health 7, 8, 9, and 10, divided in a group of area-connected provinces that had populations in each Area Health about 3-6 millions. Thus, there were 4 pilot districts on the projects' implementations which the authors should respectively set their names as district A, B, C, D by the success level on achieving the 7 aspects.

1.6 Research Conceptual Framework

The development of the learning rural case study of action state policies through the use of health impact assessment application program and the conceptual framework was determined by the authors with experts'

evaluations. there is an evaluation during the implementation by applying 6 steps of Health Impact assessment (HIA): 1) screening; 2) setting the scope and approaches; 3) evaluation; 4) reviewing the draft report; 5) developing proposals for improvement; and 6) monitoring, evaluation and revision. Sutheravut,(2020: 55), and Chantarasombat& Meekhamtong, (2020: 13-14). As shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The conceptual framework of the study of developing the program of action state policy through use of health impact Assessment application of value intelligent

3. Methods

3.1 The projects' procedures

The Quality-of-Life Development committees were enhanced to be able to manage their funding projects by working along with government and private sectors in their districts to get the well-being of health quality. The committees were expected to get knowledge about the project details in terms of framework, criteria, scope, mechanisms and evaluation methods before having discussion on the project objectives. The project had 3 groups of stakeholders; academic groups, mentor groups, and implement groups to work in target areas of pilot districts from each Area Health. The academic group at the central sector had set the procedures and techniques for the project, created the project handbooks and assessment tools, such as an online program, then did workshops with the mentor groups who would be coaches to the implement groups.

Bureaucratized hierarchy was used in the project procedures. There were the committees at province, district, and sub-district levels. The mentor groups were set at Area Health regional level and the pilot district levels to work as the selected projects consultant clinics. The implement groups were the Quality-of-Life Development committee in district and sub-district levels. They took their roles as project presenters, project

managers, and project assessment teams. The project consultant clinics and the assessment reports were forced to do via the online program.

Online meetings and workshops were used as the process techniques. The workshops were done at 3 steps. The first one was coaching the mentors at regional level to be able to know how to support and develop sub-district health funding projects and how to use assessment program systems via the internet. The second one was coaching the mentors at the pilot district to know how to analyze the public health problems and how to follow up the sub-district health funding projects. The last one was setting the meeting forum with the Quality-of-Life Development committees and representatives from each sub-district who were responsive in the pilot area to discuss their communities health problems, consultations, revising, and selecting the funding projects. Focus groups, check lists, monthly meeting platform reports, observation, and interviewing the individual participant were used in the workshops that based on problem + KPI in order to approve the projects. The selected funding projects were followed up at least 3 times in each pilot area, and were all evaluated and revised by the working teams before reporting on the online program.

3.2 Research Methods

The project took place between July 2019-November 2020. The working groups from each Area Health had to fill out the final reports via the online program on April, 2020. Document analysis was used to analyze the final reports.

4. Results

The final reports analysis of the 4 pilot districts showed us that although we used the same projects' procedures, techniques, and mechanisms, there were different levels of the projects' achievements in Northeastern Area Healths as presented on Table 1. [insert - Table 1. The Project Achievements in Northeastern Area Healths - here]

The results of the project that we had analyzed should be summarized into 3 P's: Process, People, and Program as follows:

1. Process

The strength points of the process were the development of individuals potential in the mentor teams at both regional and district levels that they were able to analyze the health situation in the area and used online databases recording to follow up the selected projects. As a result, they had the assessment skills and the methods of analyzing the health situation and problems in the area which could be used to find out the ways for enhancing their better health situation in their communities through the district health funds (District A, B). In contrast, the project's process had its weakness that the period for developing work plans was limited to the fiscal year. The budget had been proved by the local fund committees before the health promotion projects were selected. Therefore, some projects were implemented without developing steps and up-to-date situations (District A, C). Besides this, the working teams were outsiders who did not work with nor work within the implement groups' organizations so they had no direct effects, whether the positive nor negative one, to command the groups in driving the projects (District B, C). District B also complained about the projects' funding that was too strict to the financial management regulations and under controlled the local funding managers' policies.

2. People

Horizontal and vertical cooperation from individuals and networks were said as main factors to achieve the projects' goals (District A, B, C). Potential leaders of the committees, communities or networks, who were cleared on their roles, were identified as important persons for supporting the projects (District A, C). However, shortage of time on the project period made incomplete results on achieving all 7 aspects of the project. Most implement groups had not enough time to get on their new knowledge to be able to clearly understand the procedures and mechanisms of the project. Besides this, there were some workers' replacements during the process that made the projects' burden (District A, D). Even though they had corporations, they did not have strong systematic collaboration enough to complete their work roles by themselves, for example, local officers had to take the role instead of the communities in expanding working areas (District A), incomplete assessment on the online program (District B), did not fill out the program report but reported the projects' activities via Line as they used to do (District C), or having exceeded expectations that the online program should be able to set priority on the area health problems with appropriate suggestions to solve them (District D).

3. Program

Online program was set by the academic group as the projects' mechanism for filling out the projects reports on the 7 aspects. It was a new program that did not had any real trials yet. Thus, it was not surprising that the program had been mostly reported on its weakness as a complicated, difficult to imply, and

unable to link to necessary databases on other programs, especially with the National Health Security Office (NHSO) Local Funds program, one (District A, C, D). The NHSO Local Funds program was an important one because the NHSO normally allocated annual budgets on rural health security projects, the National Health Security Local Fund, through the Department of Local Administration who had the National Health Security Local Fund committees at sub-district level to select and present the health projects in the area to receive the funds each fiscal year. Therefore, District A and D commented on the programs' duplication that increased the implement groups' workloads.

Only District A had positive thinking on the online program as a supporting mechanism to be able to do more projects. With the program, the committees of District A had health situation databases on district and sub-district levels that could be used in further health promotion projects, or could be integrated into other organizations' health promotion projects. Moreover, they could learn about health problems in other Areas Health in the country as well. The program guideline that was used for systematically operating the selected projects were available to activities practice in the area and could be followed up the projects through the assessment steps.

Suggestions were also included in the final reports on the 3 P's, Process, People, and Program as follows:

1. The projects' process should integrate the mentors groups in both regional and district levels to guide and exchange the project's advancements (District A, B). It should be clearly identified on the participation roles in each step of the projects' activities so that the implement groups exactly know the contact person/organization who could motivate the projects' activities (District A, B, D). The projects' assessment should be similar to other concerned health promotion fundings projects (District B). District A suggested that other projects' outcomes should be included in the indicators, such as the ability to decrease health problems in the area, or increasing of new generation leaders who had positive participation working attitudes.

2. The people concerned were suggested that the project should have potential working teams who had enough experience and understanding on the projects' scope to be the core persons in developing the selected projects (District A, B, C). The concerned civil service staff should cooperative with the coaching teams to follow up the selected projects because of their having direct positive or negative working effects on the implement groups (District C). The Quality-of-Life Development committees and their networks at sub-district level should be enhanced to be able to effectively manage the projects by themselves in every aspect (District A, C, D).

3. The program was suggested that it should be link to the database of, or used the National Health Security Local Fund program instead in order to decrease duplication workloads (District A, B, D). It should be designed to be more friendly usage (District A, D)- should be developed to be an application on mobile phones, for example (District D). Besides this, it should not focus only on the capital report results, but should reflect the roles of other agencies who also took the roles in monitoring the projects at the district level, too (District A).

5. Discussion

The capacity building enhancing efficiency of an individual health promoter (Smith, Tang and Nutbeam, 2006) was clearly shown as affected factors to the Integrated Enhancement of Health Program and Development of Health Mechanism at Area Level Project that had distributed in the Northeastern region, Thailand. Though a few different details occurred according to the social backgrounds, local participation in the action state project in Thailand, where her rural citizens had a few chance in political commitment through her long history, still shown us the success factors in transforming the state policies/projects to public participants of Zadeh and Ahmad (2009), Aarts and Leeuwis (2010), Chifamba (2013), and Pagatpathan and Ward (2017).

On studying the final reports of 4 pilot districts, we found different success levels of the projects occurred during the implementation step. Networking in 360 degrees directions was mostly agreed as the main factor for local participation success (District A, B, C), especially those between the civil officers and local villagers, corresponds to the study of Aarts and Leeuwis (2010). With the well-balanced relationship between the state and the participants, the civil staff networks could motivate the local participation projects to achieve their goals, such as District A could achieved their projects the most because the District Chief of District A took his role as a good supporter and asked the projects' managers to sign in the Memorandum of Understanding with him. In contrast, with high authorities in bureaucratic systems, the projects were obstructed, such as the committees of District B were forced to do the projects that were strictly under the local funding managers' policies which did not exactly respond to the local health problems situation or the committees at District C did not report even the name of the selected projects on their final report because their implement working teams had used Line to report the projects' advancements instead of using the project online program.

Thus, the results confirmed the concept of capacity building on the concerned organization support that affected the effectiveness of the health promotion strategies (Smith, Tang and Nutbeam, 2006).

Strong bureaucratic systems also made the project process separate from cooperation with other agencies. The Office of the Thai Health Promotion Foundation (ThaiHealth), National Health Security Office (NHSO), and the Ministry of Public Health had integrated the project while cutting off an integration with the Department of Local Administration, under the Ministry of Interior, who was a responsible agency of the National Health Security Local Fund and already had its funding committees at sub-district level. As a result, the funding committees in some pilot districts had already selected the health projects in the area to receive the funds in the fiscal year before the project started its implementation step. Besides this, the project program was not designed to be able to link databases with the National Health Security Local Fund program that made the Quality-of-Life Development committees, who may occasionally be in the National Health Security Local Fund committees, complained about its complicated datasets that increased their workloads.

Participants should take their roles effectively if they received enough knowledge and information concerned which was a characteristic of capacity building concept on knowledge and skills advancement among practitioners (Smith, Tang and Nutbeam, 2006). On the other hand, general villagers had not enough specific skills to develop the state project effectively if they had not in-depth information and widespread networks. They asked for help from mentors in both regional and district level before and during the project or else they would let the role of the project motivation to the civil officers' responsibility. Lacking time to complete the project in the term of the fiscal year and the online program was on trial during coaching workshops, the mentors at district level who had attended the workshops, that mainly focused on monitoring and recording the data recording program online, did not quite understand or had adequate knowledge regarding to the program using and found that the program was quite difficult and complicated to use. Therefore, they made their own decisions that the program should be started to be used first only with a group of people who would be able to practice. They expected that when this group was skillful, they would further expand the knowledge to the communities groups. The decision might cause the committees in District C to report their projects' advancement via Line instead of filling out the online program because they were not enhanced with the needed knowledge on using the program.

Appropriate coaching lead to appropriate selected the local health solution projects beneath the Sub-District committees responsiveness. District A could imply their selected projects to practice the best comparing to other pilot districts because they selected only 3 contexts that they could manage by their communities empowerment, corresponding to the study of Chifamba (2013) that the communities had more participations in the state projects that affected directly to their communities or their nearby one and the project context should not beyond their limited power.

6. Conclusions

Integrated Enhancement of Health Program and Development of Health Mechanism at Area Level Project was an integrated project of the organizations under the Ministry of Public Health, Thailand, with one of its objectives to increase local participation in solving their districts health problems in their communities area. The procedures, methods, and mechanisms were set as a tailor program to all Area Healths in the country. This article studied the success levels of the project in 4 Areas Health in the Northeastern region. We found the different levels of success in each Area Health. The success factors on well-balanced participation roles between the state and the villagers participants was a dominant one. Though the usefulness of the project caused operational change in individual, organizations, and even community groups, feedback from the local participants on the project should be carefully considered by the state to improve and revise the state project in order to create sustainable partnerships for health promotion achievements in rural communities.

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